

Supplementary material for the manuscript entitled 'Food marketing on the International Food and Beverage Alliance's Mexican websites during COVID-19' by Nieto C, et al.

Supplementary Annex 2. Codebook to explore Mexican Websites committed to the International Food and Beverage Alliance.

Concept	Technical definition	Operational definition	Code/example	Reference
BEFORE STARTING: 1) DELETE HISTORY AND COOKIES 2) ENTER INCOGNITO MODE 3) START RECORDING IN SOFTWARE				
Consecutive_number	Consecutive page number to be explored, this number should be in the first column A of excel. The numbers must be consecutive 1,2,3,4,5 etc.	Consecutive page number to be explored, this number should be in the first column A of excel. The numbers must be consecutive 1,2,3,4,5 etc.	1-1000	NA
Website_number	Number taken from the database constructed according to the brands to be evaluated. This number must match the tab pages to be explored.	Number taken from the database constructed according to the brands to be evaluated. This number must match the tab pages to be explored.	1-1000	NA
Website_visited	Copy the link of the visited website	Copy the link of the visited website	https://www.trident.com.mx/producto.html?idproduct	

Incognito mode	Write down 1 when the page was entered to browse in incognito mode. The variable serves as a reminder.	Write down 1 when the page was entered to browse in incognito mode. The variable serves as a reminder.	0=no; 1=yes	NA
Date	Enter the date you visited the website	Enter the date you visited the website	16/03/20	NA
Start_time	Enter the time when you visited the website	Enter the time when you visited the website	14:34	NA
Recording	It serves as a reminder to start recording, you must answer if you have recorded or not. Preferably record all visits	It serves as a reminder to start recording, you must answer if you have recorded or not. Preferably record all visits	0=no; 1=yes	NA
Observer	Answer the corresponding code for the observer	Answer the corresponding code for the observer		NA
Mexico_page	When the web page of the brand or product states that it belongs to the country, or the domain is for Mexico (ending ".mx").	When the web page of the brand or product states that it belongs to the country, or the domain is for Mexico (ending ".mx").	0=no; 1=yes	J. Postel. RFC 1591 - Domain Name System Structure and Delegation. 1994. Available in http://www.faqs.org/rfcs/rfc1591.html . Consulted 25/01/2020.

Brand	Write down the brand to which the product belongs. For example: Danonino and DanUp belong to the Danone brand. Remember to write in capital letters and without accents.	Write down the brand to which the product belongs. For example: Danonino and DanUp belong to the Danone brand. Remember to write in capital letters and without accents.	DANONE	NA
Product	Write down the product. For example: Danonino and DanUp. Remember to write in capital letters and without accents.	Write down the product. For example: Danonino and DanUp. Remember to write in capital letters and without accents.	DANONINO	NA
Beverages_food	Answer if it is food, drink, both or fast food	Answer if it is food, drink, both or fast food	1=food 2=beverages 3=both 4=Fast food (McDonalds, Pizza Hut, Burger King) 5=liquid/syrup 6=powder	NA
Marketing directed to children	Any message or content that is directed at children, appeals to children, or is in the media tested, to which children are exposed. Examples of such advertising include the use of colors, voices, images, music or sounds that appeal to children, or	To identify if the website targets children, the following can be evaluated: 1) cartoon or children's TV show characters, toys that appeal to children under 12 years of age. Consider anthropomorphized objects such as	0=no 1=marketing directed to children	Pan American Health Organization. Recommendations of the Pan American Health Organization expert consultation on the promotion and advertising of foods and nonalcoholic beverages to children in the Americas region. Washington, D.C. PAHO, 2011. Harris, J., Schwartz, M., & Brownell, K. (2010). Marketing foods to children and adolescents: Licensed

	<p>activities, such as collecting or drawing, that are likely to be popular with children, or characters with whom children are likely to identify.</p>	<p>smiling fruits, spoons or animals), and visual-spatial games (word search puzzle).</p>		<p>characters and other promotions on packaged foods in the supermarket. <i>Public Health Nutrition</i>, 13(3), 409-417.</p> <p>Cruz-Casarrubias C, Tolentino-Mayo L, Nieto C, Théodore FL, Monterrubio-Flores E. Use of advertising strategies to target children in sugar-sweetened beverages packaging in Mexico and the nutritional quality of those beverages. <i>Pediatr Obes</i>. 2021 Feb;16(2):e12710.</p>
<p>Examples:</p>				
<p>Marketing directed to adolescents</p>	<p>All marketing material found in schools, places frequented by teenagers, internet, toys, or any product with the logo of food or beverage</p>	<p>To identify if the website targets teenagers, the following can be evaluated: websites that show personalities from</p>	<p>0=no 1=marketing directed to adolescents</p>	<p>Story et al. Food Advertising and Marketing Directed at Children and Adolescents in the US. <i>Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act</i> 2004; 1, (3). 2.</p> <p>Chan et al. Impact of celebrity endorsement in advertising on</p>

	<p>companies, or that are promoted by "idols" or celebrities.</p>	<p>teen TV shows, PG-13 movies (even if they include alcohol, bars, nightclubs, profanity, violence, nudity). Other types of entertainment such as celebrities (including athletes) and any type of sport.</p>		<p>brand image among Chinese adolescents. <i>Young Consumers</i>, 2013; 14(2), 167–179.</p> <p>Harris, J., Schwartz, M., & Brownell, K. (2010). Marketing foods to children and adolescents: Licensed characters and other promotions on packaged foods in the supermarket. <i>Public Health Nutrition</i>, 13(3), 409-417.</p>
<p>Examples:</p>		<p>0=no; 1=yes</p>	<p>World Health Organisation. A framework for implementing the set of recommendations on the marketing of foods and non-alcoholic beverages to children. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organisation; 2012.</p>	
<p>Brand_character</p>	<p>Character developed by a company to promote a food, drink or the brand itself.</p>	<p>Any character or mascot represented on the page developed by the brand, includes human beings, animals or any object. For example: Tigre Toño, Melvin, Pancho Pantera.</p>		

Examples:

Licensed_character

Being given unique characteristics including animals or any object

Cartoons and third-party characters, including characters from movies, books, TV shows and the internet. Can be licensed characters, e.g., "Dora the Explorer", "Minions" etc. (excludes humans who are not playing animated characters).

0=no; 1=yes

Vassallo et al. Junk Food Marketing on Instagram: Content Analysis. JMIR Public Health Surveill 2018;4(2): e54. 2. Freeman et al. Digital junk: food and beverage marketing on Facebook. Am J Public Health. 2014;104(12): e56-64.

Examples:

<p>Celebrities</p>	<p>People dedicated to entertainment</p>	<p>Well-known entertainment celebrities who appear in various media, excluding athletes or sportsmen. Celebrities can promote the product in different ways, for example: giving testimonials of product use, acting as endorsers of the product, or consuming the product.</p>	<p>0=no; 1=yes</p>	<p>Vassallo et al. Junk Food Marketing on Instagram: Content Analysis. JMIR Public Health Surveill 2018;4(2):e54. 2. Freeman et al. Digital junk: food and beverage marketing on Facebook. Am J Public Health. 2014;104(12):e56-64. 3. Blackwell et al. Consumer Behavior: An Asia Pacific Approach, Thomson, Melbourne. 2006</p>
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Examples:

<p>Advergames</p>	<p>Games and/or advergames related to the company, brand or product: Website or entertainment application developed by or in collaboration with food and beverage companies.</p>	<p>Online games and/or interactive entertainment applications that highlight the brand. The product is an integral part of the game, for example an obstacle or the character through which it interacts.</p>	<p>0=no; 1=yes</p>	<p>Culp et al. Characteristics of Food Industry Web Sites and “Advergames” Targeting Children. <i>Nutrit Edu and Beh.</i> 2010;42(3), 197–201. 2. Giallourakis T. Advergames. http://advergames.com/about.php. Accessed January 25, 2020.</p>
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Examples:

<p>Movie_moment</p>	<p>Movie that is currently or in the last 6 months on the billboards of Mexican theaters. You must include the name of the movie, not just the character.</p>	<p>Movie that is currently or in the last 6 months on the billboards of Mexican theaters. You must include the name of the movie, not just the character.</p>	<p>0=no; 1=yes</p>	<p>NA</p>
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Examples:

<p>social_media_links</p>	<p>Element that contains a specific address and when clicked it directs you to it.</p>	<p>Any icon or link that redirects the brand or product page to a social network such as Twitter, Facebook and Instagram.</p>	<p>0=no; 1=yes</p>	<p>Vassallo et al. Junk Food Marketing on Instagram: Content Analysis. JMIR Public Health Surveill 2018;4(2):e54. 2. Freeman et al. Digital junk: food and beverage marketing on Facebook. Am J Public Health. 2014;104(12):e56-64</p>
<p>Hashtag</p>	<p>Word or phrase preceded by the # sign used in a message as a keyword to promote a product and facilitate search in Internet applications such as Facebook or Twitter</p>	<p>Any word preceded by the # sign that is displayed on the website.</p>	<p>0=no; 1=yes</p>	<p>Jaichuen et al. Food Marketing in Facebook to Thai Children and Youth: An Assessment of the Efficacy of Thai Regulations. Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2019, 16(7): 1204</p>

Examples:

Examples:

<p>Which</p>	<p>#Nadiepuedecomersol oua the hashtag must be written as it appears on the page, if there are several, they must all be written</p>	<p>#Nadiepuedecomersol oua the hashtag must be written as it appears on the page, if there are several, they must all be written</p>	<p>#destapalafelicidad</p>	<p>NA</p>
<p>COVID-19 strategy</p>	<p>Reference to the pandemic, mentions of COVID-19, staying at home, social distancing, or safety measure like wearing masks, glasses, and/or face shields.</p>	<p>The website displayed any reference to the pandemic, mentions of COVID-19, staying at home, social distancing, or safety measure like showing a person or a character wearing masks, glasses, and/or face shields.</p>	<p>0=no; 1=yes</p>	<p>NA</p>

Examples:

<p>End_time</p>	<p>Write the time when you finished visiting the website</p>	<p>Write the time when you finished visiting the website</p>	<p>Example 14:34</p>	<p>NA</p>
<p>Visit_time</p>	<p>The time spent visiting the website must be timed. Time spent seeking social responsibility and protection for children is not counted</p>	<p>The time spent visiting the website must be timed. Time spent seeking social responsibility and protection for children is not counted</p>	<p>Example 3:35</p>	<p>NA</p>
<p>Responsibility_philanthropy</p>	<p>A company voluntarily donates financially or in-kind support to a social cause or non-profit organization.</p>	<p>Promotion of any sustainability initiatives, ethics or charity work undertaken by the brand or product.</p>	<p>0=no; 1=yes</p>	<p>Ricks, J.M., Williams, J.A. Strategic Corporate Philanthropy: Addressing Frontline Talent Needs Through an Educational Giving Program. J Bus Ethics 2005; 60, 147–157.</p>